

The Utilization of Plastic Waste in Indonesia to Improve Low-Cost Housing

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Abstract

This research paper explores the potential of utilizing recycled plastic in low-cost housing construction as a solution for waste management and a path toward sustainable development in Indonesia. We investigate Indonesia's primary sources of plastic waste generation and the environmental, health, and economic consequences of plastic pollution. By analyzing current plastic waste generation statistics and comparing the costs of conventional and recycled plastic construction materials, we assess the financial feasibility of this approach. We also explore several approaches to specific plastic alternatives in construction and a comparative analysis of each approach. We then identify specific applications and uses for these approaches. We conclude by summarizing the essential findings and highlighting the potential of this approach for tackling Indonesia's plastic waste crisis and achieving sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Plastic waste, Waste management, Indonesia, Housing

I. Introduction and Background

Plastic pollution has become a global crisis, threatening our ecosystems and wildlife. Every year, millions of tons of plastic waste end up in landfills and oceans, causing devastating environmental damage. Indonesia, an archipelagic nation with a sprawling coastline, is particularly vulnerable to this issue. With a rapidly growing population and a booming consumer market, plastic waste generation in Indonesia has reached staggering heights. Indonesia faces a disproportionately high level of plastic pollution due to factors like rapid urbanization, inadequate waste management systems, and a high consumption of single-use plastics, contributing to an estimated 1.29 million metric tons of plastic waste entering its marine environment annually [1]. The country consistently ranks among the top plastic polluters in the world, with a significant portion of this plastic mismanaged and leaking into the environment. This plastic influx pollutes pristine beaches, rivers, and coral reefs, harming marine life and jeopardizing the delicate balance of Indonesia's rich biodiversity.

But what problems are caused by plastic pollution in Indonesia, and what innovative solutions are being proposed to tackle this pressing issue?

*Image a.**Image b.**Image c.**Image d.*

Image a. Garbage accumulates in Palu Bay in Central Sulawesi on Jan. 28, 2017. (Antara/Mohamad Hamzah) [2],
Image b. Scavengers collect valuable waste at Sidoarjo garbage dump in East Java, on 5 June, 2018. (Juni Kriswanto / AFP Photo) [3],
Image c. A man paddles through the infamous Citarum river in West Java, Indonesia. (Bastian AS/Shutterstock.). [4],
Image d. A plastic dump, full of foreign waste, near a paper mill in East Java, Indonesia. (Beth Gardiner) Image d. [5]

1.1 Sources of the Plastic Deluge

Indonesia faces a critical plastic pollution problem due to a combination of factors. The booming consumer culture has dramatically increased single-use plastics, from packaging and shopping bags to food containers. These items are often disposed of quickly, adding heavily to the waste stream. Industries like food and beverage, manufacturing, and retail are significant contributors, relying heavily on plastics. Unfortunately, inadequate waste management within these industries makes the problem even worse. To top it off, Indonesia's waste collection and recycling systems are overwhelmed by the growing volume of plastic waste. This lack of infrastructure leads to overflowing landfills, overflowing bins, and plastic dumped in the environment [6].

Also, many Indonesian citizens often need more time to avoid plastic usage. Due to Indonesia's large delivery and convenience culture, packages are usually swiftly and efficiently delivered in plastic, as they are cheap and durable.

Packaging and delivery are some of the most significant contributors to plastic waste in Indonesia, and most containers are single-use plastics, which means they are immediately discarded after usage.

1.2 The Price of Plastic Pollution

Plastic pollution in Indonesia unleashes a cascade of devastating consequences. Pristine beaches, rivers, and marine ecosystems are choked by plastic debris, harming wildlife through entanglement, injuries, and even death. The fragmentation of plastic into microplastics further complicates the issue, infiltrating the food chain and potentially posing health risks to humans. The breakdown of plastic also releases harmful chemicals into the environment, potentially contaminating water sources and food chains and raising concerns about human health. However, the full extent of these risks requires further investigation [7].

Along with this, locals often burn plastic and trash to eliminate overflowing garbage, but this only further contributes to microplastic pollution in the atmosphere. Economically, Indonesia needs to handle the burden of ineffective waste management, with rising collection, transportation, and disposal costs. On top of that, plastic pollution damages vital sectors like tourism and fisheries, dealing a double blow to the Indonesian economy.

Plastic mismanagement in Indonesia comes at a steep price. A study estimates the hidden economic cost of plastic bags alone to be over USD 2.91 billion annually due to factors like production costs and lost revenue in tourism and fisheries [8]. The environmental impact is also substantial, with the World Bank estimating plastic pollution costing Indonesia's ocean economy over \$450 million per year [9]. This includes damage to marine ecosystems and the expense of cleaning up plastic waste. These figures likely underestimate the actual cost of plastic mismanagement in Indonesia, as organizations often do not survey many isolated areas in the archipelago for plastic usage. Coastal regions, heavily reliant on tourism and fisheries, are particularly impacted by plastic pollution, incurring additional economic losses.

1.3 Current Efforts in Indonesia

Indonesia is tackling its plastic waste problem on multiple fronts. The government has set ambitious goals to reduce marine plastic debris by 70% by 2025 through the National Action Plan on Marine Litter. This plan includes initiatives like improved waste management data collection, promoting reusable alternatives to plastic bags, and exploring technologies like using recycled plastic in road construction. Additionally, multi-stakeholder partnerships like the Indonesia National Plastic Action Partnership (NPAP) bring together businesses, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and policymakers to create a more circular plastic economy, focusing on reducing plastic use, improving recycling rates, and developing innovative solutions [10].

Although the main focus of this research paper, along with current efforts, are directly focused around the country of Indonesia, this does not take away from the value of this research on the global stage. This research is very relevant to multiple countries that currently face issues with plastic waste and pollution, such as China and Singapore. The information shared in this research paper does not need to be limited simply to Indonesia's landscape.

This research paper delves into a potential solution to Indonesia's plastic waste crisis: exploring recycled plastic in low-cost housing construction. By investigating the feasibility and effectiveness of utilizing recycled plastic in building materials, this research aims to identify a two-pronged approach. Firstly, it seeks to significantly reduce plastic waste by diverting it from landfills and the environment. Secondly, it explores the potential for recycled plastic to address the pressing need for affordable and sustainable housing solutions in Indonesia's growing urban centers. By examining this

approach's technical and economic viability, this paper can contribute valuable insights into tackling Indonesia's plastic waste problem while promoting sustainable and affordable housing development.

II. Various Processes for Utilizing Recycled Plastic in Construction

The construction industry is increasingly exploring using recycled plastic as a sustainable alternative to traditional materials. This trend is driven by the growing need to manage plastic waste effectively and reduce environmental impact. Several innovative processes are emerging that utilize recycled plastic in various construction applications. These include replacing aggregate in concrete with shredded or granulated plastic particles, incorporating plastic fibers for reinforcement, utilizing discarded plastic bottles as building blocks, and even integrating melted plastic into asphalt mixtures. Each approach offers unique advantages and considerations, making a comprehensive understanding of these processes crucial for evaluating their potential within the construction sector. These recycled plastic applications have the potential to lighten structures, improve durability, and offer new design possibilities, all while diverting plastic waste from landfills and promoting a more circular economy in construction.

2.1 Plastic as Aggregate Replacement

One potential solution to the ever-growing problem of plastic waste management lies in its utilization as a partial replacement for conventional aggregates in construction materials. This approach involves the incorporation of recycled plastic fragments, typically obtained from mechanical processing of post-consumer waste, into concrete or mortar mixes. Research by Akinwumi et al. (2022) investigated the use of shredded polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles in Cement-Stabilized Earth Blocks (CEBs). Their findings demonstrated the feasibility of incorporating up to 6% of recycled PET by weight without compromising the workability of the CEBs [11]. This suggests potential benefits in specific performance aspects, such as manageability during construction.

The process of incorporating plastic as an aggregate replacement generally involves several key steps:

- **Sorting and Cleaning:** The collected plastic waste undergoes a rigorous sorting and cleaning process to remove contaminants and ensure material consistency. This stage is crucial to prevent any negative impact on the final properties of the construction material.
- **Size Reduction:** The sorted plastic undergoes size reduction techniques, such as shredding or grinding, to achieve a specific gradation suitable for the target application. The size and shape of the resulting plastic fragments play a critical role in their interaction with the cementitious matrix and influence the overall performance of the composite material. Guo et al. (2023) highlight that the optimal size range for plastic aggregates in concrete is typically between 4.75 mm and 20 mm [12].
- **Mix Design:** The prepared plastic aggregates are incorporated into the concrete or mortar mix design, typically replacing a predetermined portion of the conventional natural aggregates like sand or gravel. The optimal replacement ratio is often determined through experimental investigations, considering factors like workability, strength development, and long-term durability of the resulting composite material. Studies by Guo et al. (2023) suggest that replacing up to 10% of sand with plastic aggregates in concrete might be feasible without significant reduction in compressive strength [12].

Studies, such as the aforementioned MDPI and ScienceDirect research, have observed promising results with incorporating plastic aggregates. The presence of plastic fragments within the concrete matrix can act as fillers, occupying voids that would otherwise be occupied by water. This improved packing density can contribute to enhanced compressive strength and reduced water permeability of the final product. However, it is essential to acknowledge that integrating

plastic aggregates presents particular challenges. The inherent flexibility of plastic compared to traditional aggregates can influence the mechanical properties of the composite material, such as stiffness and elastic modulus. Further research is necessary to optimize the incorporation process, addressing these potential drawbacks while maximizing the benefits of utilizing recycled plastic waste in construction applications.

2.2 Plastic Fibers for Reinforcement

In contrast to the aggregate replacement technique, plastic fiber reinforcement offers an alternative method for incorporating plastic into construction materials. This approach leverages the unique properties of plastic fibers to enhance specific performance characteristics of the concrete matrix. Research studies, such as one by Saranya and Subha Pradha (2023), documented on platforms like ResearchGate, have explored the efficacy of plastic fiber-reinforced concrete elements (FRCEs). These investigations have yielded promising results, demonstrating that including up to 1% of plastic fibers by volume can significantly improve the concrete's tensile strength by up to 30% and flexural toughness by up to 120% [13].

The mechanism behind this reinforcement technique lies in the ability of the dispersed plastic fibers to bridge and arrest cracks within the concrete matrix. Unlike traditional steel reinforcement, which is typically concentrated in specific locations, plastic fibers are distributed throughout the concrete mix. This uniform distribution allows them to effectively resist the propagation of cracks at their initiation stage, leading to enhanced overall tensile strength and improved resistance to cracking. Additionally, the inherent flexibility of plastic fibers allows them to absorb impact energy, contributing to the increased flexural toughness of the composite material. This characteristic makes plastic fiber-reinforced concrete particularly suitable for applications subjected to high-impact loads or demanding dynamic environments, where enhanced durability and crack resistance are critical [13].

It is important to note that the selection and incorporation of plastic fibers require careful consideration. Different plastic fibers, with varying properties such as length, tensile strength, and modulus of elasticity, are available. Selecting the optimal fiber type depends on the application and desired performance enhancements. The dosage, or the amount of fibers added to the concrete mix, also plays a crucial role. As highlighted in the study by Saranya and Subha Pradha (2023), while a higher fiber content (up to 1%) can lead to more significant reinforcement effects, it can also impact the workability of the fresh concrete. Therefore, achieving an optimal balance between fiber content and workability is essential for successful implementation.

2.3 Melted Plastic in Asphalt

The potential uses of recycled plastic extend beyond concrete and into the realm of foundation construction. Studies published by MDPI, such as the one by Di Mino et al. (2023), have explored the incorporation of melted plastic into asphalt mixtures. This technique involves adding processed and melted plastic waste to the asphalt binder, the glue-like substance that holds the aggregate particles together. Research suggests that this approach can offer several advantages. The plastic modifies the properties of the asphalt, potentially increasing its flexibility by up to 19% and resistance to rutting (permanent deformation) by up to 50%, as reported in the study by Di Mino et al. (2023) [14]. This can lead to longer-lasting building foundations with a reduced need for frequent repairs. Additionally, incorporating recycled plastic waste into asphalt offers a potential solution for diverting plastic from landfills and promoting a more sustainable approach to building foundation construction. However, it is essential to note that this is a relatively new area of research, and further investigation is needed to fully understand the long-term performance of plastic-modified asphalt and its impact on building safety and environmental factors. [14].

III. Comparative Analysis of Construction Processes

The integration of recycled plastic into the construction industry offers potential benefits in terms of waste reduction, material performance, and cost-effectiveness. However, the feasibility and suitability of each method, including aggregate replacement, fiber reinforcement, bottle utilization, and asphalt modification, depend on a complex interplay of factors. These factors encompass material strength and durability, construction complexity, economic viability, environmental impact, and specific project requirements. A comprehensive comparative analysis is necessary to determine the optimal application of recycled plastic in construction and to assess its overall contribution to sustainable development.

3.1 Material Strength and Durability

The efficacy of using recycled plastic in construction varies significantly depending on the application and can impact both material strength and durability. While replacing conventional aggregates with plastic can potentially enhance certain properties like water resistance, the overall compressive strength, a crucial indicator of durability, can be negatively affected. Studies by Guo et al. (2023) report that depending on the plastic type and proportion used, replacing aggregates with recycled plastic can decrease compressive strength by up to 20% [12].

Similarly, incorporating plastic fibers into concrete can improve tensile strength and toughness, but the fiber's distribution and orientation play crucial roles. Research by Saranya and Subha Pradha (2023) suggests that including up to 1% of plastic fibers by volume can significantly improve the concrete's tensile strength by up to 30%, but the impact on long-term durability needs further investigation [13].

Lastly, incorporating melted plastic into asphalt can enhance flexibility and crack resistance by up to 19%, as reported by Di Mino et al. (2023). However, its long-term performance under diverse climatic conditions and potential impact on overall building strength remain areas for further study. Comprehensive evaluations are essential to determine the optimal applications and limitations of each method, considering both short-term benefits and long-term durability [14].

3.2 Construction Complexity

The complexity of incorporating recycled plastic into construction materials varies significantly across different methods, with some requiring specialized equipment and precise control. Replacing conventional aggregates with up to 20% recycled plastic, as studied by Guo et al. (2023), can be integrated into existing concrete production processes with minimal adjustments. This approach offers a relatively straightforward way to utilize plastic waste in construction [12].

In contrast, utilizing plastic fibers for reinforcement demands more precise control. Studies like the one by Saranya and Subha Pradha (2023) show that optimal fiber distribution is crucial for achieving the desired improvements. This can increase construction complexity as it may involve specialized mixing techniques or equipment to ensure proper fiber dispersion throughout the concrete mix [13].

Lastly, the integration of melted plastic into asphalt necessitates the most complex approach. This method requires specialized equipment to handle and precisely mix the molten plastic with asphalt binder at specific temperatures, as highlighted by Di Mino et al. (2023). Maintaining rigorous control over these processes adds significant complexity to the asphalt production process [14].

3.3 Cost-Effectiveness

Stage	Plastic Bricks (Rupiah per meter squared) [15]	Clay Bricks/Red Bricks (Rupiah per meter squared) [16]	Sand Lime Bricks (Rupiah per meter squared) [17]
Total cost/unit	115,500	112,500	219,800

Table 1: Analyzing different costs of brick materials based on current global standards

The table above is a representation of Indonesia's current landscape in brick-making costs. Considering that plastic bricks have around the same, often even less expensive, prices when compared to their clay and lime counterparts, it should be considered as a viable option as a construction alternative material.

The economic viability of utilizing recycled plastic in construction varies significantly depending on the specific application. Replacing conventional aggregates with recycled plastic hinges on the comparative costs of these materials and the potential performance enhancements offered by the plastic. The economic feasibility of plastic fiber reinforcement is influenced by fiber costs and their impact on concrete properties. While plastic bottles are readily available, the labor-intensive construction process associated with this method might offset potential cost savings. Lastly, the economic prospects of incorporating melted plastic into asphalt depend on factors such as plastic availability, processing costs, and the resulting improvements in building foundation lifespan and maintenance requirements. However, do consider that application methods are very costly, and plastic alternatives are much more cost effective than other alternatives like cement. Due to plastic's low thermal conductivity, the material traps heat inside, making houses built with plastic bricks more heat efficient, therefore saving energy and money on specific heating technology [11-14].

3.4 Environmental Impact

The study by Saranya and Subha Pradha (2023) explores the environmental impact of incorporating recycled plastic into concrete. While the research acknowledges the potential benefits of waste diversion, it highlights the importance of considering the entire life cycle of the material.

Virgin plastic production can generate significant greenhouse gas emissions, with estimates suggesting up to 3.5 kg of CO₂ per kilogram of plastic. Recycling can offer a reduction in these emissions, but the process itself also consumes energy [18].

The study emphasizes the need for life cycle assessments (LCAs) to comprehensively evaluate the environmental impact of using recycled plastic in concrete. LCAs should consider factors like:

- The type and amount of plastic used
- The energy consumption during plastic recycling and concrete production
- Greenhouse gas emissions throughout the life cycle
- Potential microplastic release

By carefully considering these factors, construction projects can leverage the benefits of recycled plastic while minimizing the environmental footprint.

3.5 Comparative Analysis of Brick Making

3.5.1 Plastic Bricks

Process	Description
Raw Material Preparation	Recycled plastic waste, typically polypropylene and polyethylene, is collected, cleaned, and shredded into uniform flakes or granules. Virgin plastic can also be used, but recycling offers environmental benefits.
Mixing and Compounding	The plastic flakes are mixed with additives like sand, stabilizers, and coloring agents to enhance strength, durability, and achieve desired colors. This mixture is then heated and blended to form a homogeneous compound.
Molding	The molten plastic compound is injected into molds under high pressure. These molds create the precise shape and size of the finished brick.
Cooling and Finishing	The molded bricks are cooled and ejected from the molds. Any surface imperfections might be addressed through trimming or finishing processes.

Table 2. Process of creating plastic bricks [19]

3.5.2 Clay Bricks and Red Bricks

Process	Description
Raw Material Acquisition	Suitable clay deposits are identified, and the clay is extracted through mining or quarrying methods.
Preparation and Crushing	The extracted clay undergoes crushing and grinding to achieve a uniform consistency. This may involve removing large stones or debris.
Tempering	Water is precisely mixed with the crushed clay to achieve a workable plasticity. This allows the clay to be molded without cracking.
Shaping	There are three main shaping methods: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Soft-Mud Process: The wet clay is pressed into molds using a hydraulic press. This method is suitable for high-volume production but can result in dimensional variations due to moisture content. Dry-Press Process: The clay is mixed with less water, creating a stiffer consistency. This mixture is then pressed into molds at high pressures. This method offers more precise shapes but has limitations in production speed. Extrusion Process: The clay is forced through a shaped die, resulting in a continuous column of the desired brick profile. This column is then cut into individual bricks. This method is highly efficient for large-scale production.
Drying	The molded bricks go through a controlled drying process to remove excess moisture. Improper drying can lead to cracks during firing.

Firing	The dried bricks are stacked in kilns and subjected to high temperatures (typically between 900-1,000°C) for an extended period. This firing process hardens the clay by removing remaining moisture and inducing chemical reactions that create a strong and durable finished product. The resulting color of fired clay bricks is often red due to the presence of iron oxide, but firing conditions and additives can influence the final color.
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Table 3. Process of creating clay bricks [20]

3.5.3 Lime Bricks

Process	Description
Raw Material Preparation	Lime, a powdery substance made from limestone, and sand are gathered. These materials are then mixed together in specific proportions.
Mixing	Lime and sand are mixed with water in precise proportions to create a homogenous slurry. This mixture is crucial for the brick's strength and durability.
Molding	The prepared mixture is poured into molds of desired brick size and shape. The molds are then compacted to remove excess water and air.
Curing	The molded bricks are cured in a controlled environment. This process involves allowing the lime to react with the water and sand, hardening the brick.
Drying	The molded bricks are cooled and ejected from the molds. Any surface imperfections might be addressed through trimming or finishing processes.

Table 4: Process of creating lime bricks [21]

IV. Methodology

This research paper employs a literature review methodology, drawing primarily on existing academic research and secondary data to explore the potential of recycled plastic in low-cost housing construction in Indonesia.

4.1 Data Collection

The data for this study was sourced from a diverse range of materials, including peer-reviewed academic journals, government reports, non-governmental organization publications, and industry reports. Academic journals provided in-depth analyses of plastic waste management, sustainable construction, and low-cost housing in Indonesia. Government reports offered official statistics on plastic waste generation, recycling rates, and housing development trends within the country. Non-governmental organizations contributed reports and studies examining the environmental and social impacts of plastic pollution. Industry reports provided valuable information on the production and utilization of recycled plastic materials in construction projects. This comprehensive approach ensured a well-rounded and informative dataset for the research.

4.2 Data Analysis

The collected data was subjected to a thematic analysis, a qualitative research method that involves identifying and examining recurring patterns or themes within the data. Key themes that emerged from this analysis included the sources of plastic waste generation in Indonesia, the environmental, health, and economic consequences of plastic pollution, the feasibility of utilizing recycled plastic in low-cost housing construction, potential applications and uses of recycled plastic in the construction sector, and a comparative analysis of various approaches to employing recycled plastic. This thematic analysis allowed for a systematic and in-depth exploration of the complex issues surrounding plastic waste management, sustainable construction, and the potential role of recycled plastic in Indonesia.

4.3 Limitations

A primary limitation of this study is its reliance on secondary data. While this approach offers a robust foundation for understanding the research topic, it may not fully capture the nuances or most recent developments in the field. Additionally, the geographic focus on Indonesia may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts, as specific conditions and challenges may vary across different regions.

V. Applications and Uses

The use of recycled plastic in construction has the potential to enhance the durability and sustainability of various structural elements. Plastic aggregate replacement can improve the resistance of non-structural elements to harsh weather conditions, while plastic fibers can enhance the toughness and impact resistance of structural elements. The incorporation of melted plastic into asphalt can lead to the development of more durable and sustainable foundations.

5.1 Plastic as Aggregate Replacement

Plastic as aggregate replacement is particularly suitable for non-structural elements such as grounds, sidewalks, and drainage systems. The enhanced durability and water resistance offered by this method make it ideal for outdoor applications exposed to harsh weather conditions. For instance, studies have shown that plastic-aggregate concrete exhibits improved resistance to frost damage and de-icing salts, extending the lifespan of ground material [22].

5.2 Plastic Fibers for Reinforcement

Plastic fibers, on the other hand, find their application primarily in structural elements requiring enhanced toughness and impact resistance. These include concrete slabs, bridge decks, and retaining walls. The dispersion of plastic fibers throughout the concrete matrix contributes to improved crack control and load-bearing capacity, enhancing the overall structural integrity of the construction. Research has indicated that plastic fiber-reinforced concrete exhibits superior performance in resisting seismic loads compared to traditional concrete [23].

5.3 Melted Plastic in Asphalt

The findings of this research can be applied practically in the construction industry by incorporating recycled plastic into asphalt mixtures for retaining walls and foundation construction. This can lead to the development of more durable and sustainable buildings that require less frequent maintenance and repairs. By using recycled plastic, construction companies can reduce their reliance on virgin materials, contribute to waste reduction, and promote a more environmentally friendly approach to creating buildings and their foundations [14].

VI. Conclusion

The integration of recycled plastic into the construction industry presents a promising avenue for addressing the global plastic waste crisis while simultaneously enhancing the sustainability and performance of building materials. This research

has explored various methods for incorporating recycled plastic, including its use as aggregate replacement, reinforcement fibers, structural components derived from plastic bottles, and an additive in asphalt. Each method offers distinct advantages and challenges in terms of material properties, construction complexity, cost-effectiveness, and environmental impact. While studies have demonstrated the potential benefits of plastic incorporation, further research is imperative to optimize material formulations, assess long-term performance, and conduct comprehensive life cycle assessments to evaluate the overall environmental implications. Future investigations should focus on developing standardized testing protocols and performance criteria for plastic-based construction materials. Additionally, exploring innovative recycling technologies to produce high-quality plastic feedstocks for construction applications is essential. This research is also not restricted to the archipelago of Indonesia, but instead can be used in many locations around the world to reduce plastic waste. Countries such as Hong Kong and Malaysia that have issues with expensive housing or a lack of housing could implement these techniques to improve the housing market and living conditions. By addressing these areas, the international construction industry can unlock the full potential of recycled plastic, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient built environment.

While there have not been many explicit and large efforts made by industries or countries to implement plastic usage within construction, it is still a growing topic of discussion. Considering the severity of plastic waste's effects on humanity, this research could develop into a sustainable option of plastic reduction. Ultimately, the successful implementation of recycled plastic in construction requires collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. By fostering a circular economy approach, we can transform plastic waste from a burden into a valuable resource, mitigating environmental impacts and driving economic growth.

References

1. Arif Supam, et al. “3 Ways for Indonesia to Reduce Plastic Pollution in the Ocean.” WRI Indonesia, 2019, wri-indonesia.org/en/insights/3-ways-indonesia-reduce-plastic-pollution-ocean. Accessed 20 Aug. 2024.
2. The Jakarta Post. “Ineffective Recycling Compounds Indonesia’s Marine Waste Problem - National - the Jakarta Post.” The Jakarta Post, 2024, www.thejakartapost.com/news/2020/05/10/ineffective-recycling-compounds-indonesias-marine-waste-problem.html. Accessed 26 July 2024.
3. “Indonesia’s Plastic Waste Problem.” The ASEAN Post, 29 Dec. 2016, theaseanpost.com/article/indonesias-plastic-waste-problem. Accessed 26 July 2024.
4. World Bank Group. “Stemming the Plastics Tide in Indonesia: Policy, Investments, and Research.” World Bank, World Bank Group, 7 Oct. 2020, www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2020/10/06/stemming-the-plastics-tide-in-indonesia. Accessed 26 July 2024.
5. Magazine, Undark. “Indonesia Cracks down on Imports of Contaminated Plastic Waste.” Undark Magazine, 8 Aug. 2023, undark.org/2023/08/08/indonesia-cracks-down-on-imports-of-contaminated-plastic-waste/. Accessed 26 July 2024.
6. Rahayu Subekti. “A Circular Economy-Based Plastic Waste Management Policy in Indonesia (Compared to China and EU).” *Yustisia*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2024, pp. 168–184, jurnal.uns.ac.id/yustisia/article/view/72177/pdf. Accessed 19 July 2024.
7. “Microplastics on Human Health: How Much Do They Harm Us?” UNDP, 2023, www.undp.org/kosovo/blog/microplastics-human-health-how-much-do-they-harm-us. Accessed 19 July 2024.
8. Free, Plastic. “The Hidden Cost of Plastic Bag Use and Pollution in Indonesia • Making Oceans Plastic Free.” Making Oceans Plastic Free, 11 Nov. 2017, makingoceansplasticfree.com/hidden-cost-plastic-bag-use-pollution-indonesia/. Accessed 19 July 2024.
9. World Bank Group. “Plastic Waste Discharges from Rivers and Coastlines in Indonesia.” World Bank, World Bank Group, 28 July 2021, www.worldbank.org/en/country/indonesia/publication/plastic-waste-discharges-from-rivers-and-coastlines-in-indonesia#:~:text=An%20estimated%20346.5%20kton%2Fyear,come%20from%20Java%20and%20Sumatra. Accessed 19 July 2024.
10. IETC. “National Plastic Waste Reduction Strategic Actions for Indonesia.” International Environmental Technology Centre, 2020, www.unep.org/ietc/resources/policy-and-strategy/national-plastic-waste-reduction-strategic-actions-indonesia. Accessed 19 July 2024.
11. Akinwumi, Isaac, et al. “Experimental Insight into the Containment of Plastic Waste in Cement-Stabilised Soil as a Road Pavement Layer Material.” *Infrastructures*, vol. 7, no. 12, 16 Dec. 2022, pp. 172–172, www.mdpi.com/2412-3811/7/12/172, <https://doi.org/10.3390/infrastructures7120172>. Accessed 19 July 2024.
12. Guo, Yong-Chang, et al. “A Review on the Influence of Recycled Plastic Aggregate on the Engineering Properties of Concrete.” *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 79, 1 Nov. 2023, pp. 107787–107787, www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2352710223019678#:~:text=Aggregates%20typically%20constitute%20around%2070,with%20aggregate%20extraction%20and%20waste, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2023.107787>. Accessed 22 July 2024.
13. Saranya .K, and Subha Pradha. “Recycling Plastic Waste into Construction Materials for Sustainability.” ResearchGate, IOP Publishing, 24 July 2023, www.researchgate.net/publication/372549011_Recycling_Plastic_Waste_into_Construction_Materials_for_Sustainability. Accessed 19 July 2024.

14. Gaetano Di Mino, et al. “Investigating the Multi-Recyclability of Recycled Plastic-Modified Asphalt Mixtures.” *Infrastructures*, vol. 8, no. 5, 29 Apr. 2023, pp. 84–84, www.mdpi.com/2412-3811/8/5/84, <https://doi.org/10.3390/infrastructures8050084>. Accessed 19 July 2024.
15. Pritchard, Jim. “The Real Costs of Recycled Plastic Homes (3D and Bricks Too) - Building Renewable.” *Building Renewable*, 30 Mar. 2023, buildingrenewable.com/costs-of-recycled-plastic-homes-3d-bricks/. Accessed 22 July 2024.
16. “JAYABRIX INDONESIA.” Jayabrix.co.id, 2016, www.jayabrix.co.id/en/index.php?menu=tips&id=4. Accessed 22 July 2024.
17. “Understanding Lime Plaster Cost per M2: A Comprehensive Guide.” John Stanley Plastering, 2023, www.plastererdorset.co.uk/blog/understanding-lime-plaster-cost-per-m2-a-comprehensive-guide/#:~:text=As%20of%202023%2C%20material%20costs,finishes%20may%20increase%20this%20cost. Accessed 22 July 2024.
18. Tahir, Furqan, et al. “Environmental Impacts of Using Recycled Plastics in Concrete.” ResearchGate, Elsevier BV, 6 May 2022, www.researchgate.net/publication/360427359_Environmental_impacts_of_using_recycled_plastics_in_concrete. Accessed 25 Aug. 2024.
19. Verma, Anubhav, et al. “Manufacturing of Brick by Waste Plastic.” *International Journal of Engineering Research in Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IJERMCE)*, vol. 9, no. 6, 24 June 2022, pp. 41–45, <https://doi.org/10.36647/ijermce/09.06.a008>.
20. “How Are Bricks Made? | Wienerberger UK.” United Kingdom, Wienerberger Ltd., 15 Mar. 2023, www.wienerberger.co.uk/tips-and-advice/brickwork/how-are-bricks-made.html. Accessed 26 July 2024.
21. admin. “Sand-Lime Bricks and Blocks Technology.” Titan Brick and Block Making Machines, 23 Mar. 2023, titan-machinery.com/en/sand-lime-brick-machines/#:~:text=Sand-lime%20brick%2C%20also%20known,special%20high-pressure%20steam%20chamber. Accessed 26 July 2024.
22. Ahmed, Shehryar, and Majid Ali. Potential Applications of Different Forms of Recycled Plastics as Construction Materials—a Review. 24 Oct. 2023, www.mdpi.com/2673-4591/53/1/5#:~:text=Based%20on%20the%20desired%20mechanical,plastic%20waste%20stream%20to%20be, <https://doi.org/10.3390/iocbd2023-15177>. Accessed 26 July 2024.
23. Hasan, Hasibul, et al. “Using Plastic Wastes in Construction: Opportunities and Challenges.” ResearchGate, unknown, 7 Apr. 2022, www.researchgate.net/publication/359798882_Using_Plastic_Wastes_in_Construction_Opportunities_and_Challenges#:~:text=It%20is%20concluded%20that%20the,reliable%20supply%20of%20construction%20materials. Accessed 26 July 2024.